

An Investigation into Factors Affecting Speaking Performances of HUFU English-majored Students

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Abstract

Speaking is regarded as one of the most difficult phases of producing language in language learning (Brown & Yule, 1983). Language learners always get problems with using foreign languages to communicate effectively and fluently as they cannot find suitable words with context (Leong & Ahmadi, 2017). That becomes a big obstacle for learners, especially students in the language learning process. This study aims to investigate the factors that affecting speaking performances of English-majored students at Ho Chi Minh City University of Food Industry (HUFU). The study is carried out by using both quantitative methods and revising from related previous works. Throughout actual findings, some recommendations were given not only for students but also for teachers. The study was expected to be a useful material for students to improve their quality of speaking performances and teaching one for teachers.

Keywords: speaking skill, speaking performance, language learning

1. Introduction

Language is basically and simply created for communication. According to Cambridge Dictionary, language is “a system of communication by speaking, writing, or making signs in a way that can be understood, or any of the different systems of communication used in particular regions”. Although the internet has made changed to the ways of learning English (Nghì, 2014), speaking performance remains their own requirements and face-to-face environment.

In this era of integration, English, as a global language, becomes more and more important as its role is to connect everything and people from different countries. “People speak to maintain existing social relationships and to make new ones” (Bhattacharya, 2017). Of all four skills (listening, speaking, reading, writing) in the language learning process, speaking and writing play a major role in communication. However, speaking acts as the most significant role to achieve the purpose of communication effectively. Because you will be supposed to be a speaker of a language if you know that language (Ur, 2012). But people find it difficult to master speaking skills – a skill related to many other skills and factors. Kang Shumin (2002) stated that speaking a foreign language is not about ‘its grammatical and semantic rules’ such as accuracy of words (p. 204). However, students who have good English speaking skills and are confident enough to communicate are not many at HUFU. Most of them do not meet the requirements of teachers during school as they often lose confidence in themselves and naturally feel pressure when being called to the front to speak then even they are strongly motivated. Besides, they are afraid of being criticized or making mistakes – ‘a natural process of learning a language’ (Bhattacharya, 2017, p. 31). Therefore, teaching speaking performance has been drawn from the perspective of CBI and task-based learning teaching (Nghì, 2013).

Obviously, they believe that it is impossible to improve their speaking skill and make it master. The study is done based on the answers of English-majored students by doing a questionnaire at

HUFI. The research purposes are to review factors affecting speaking performances of students and propose suggestions to help students get to improve on speaking skills by themselves.

9. Literature review

Speaking in general

During communication activities, the learners have to keep stream words smoothly without pauses. Therefore, speaking is a complex and productive skill in four skills of language learning and much related to pronunciation (Bashir, Azeem, & Dogar, 2011). Harmer (2007) stated that 'productive skill' includes speaking and writing which are products of language generating process. When people speak at the target language that means they are creating their own products to express their ideas, emotions, and reactions to other people and in some situations, to respond to other speakers. The products are evaluated as a successful one when speakers have the ability to use language, even using non-verbal one, in a proper context. Through the pieces of evidence above, speaking is the main skill in communication that dominates the role of writing. However, it also depends on factors as fluency, intonation, stress, pronunciation, grammar, vocabulary, the speakers' skill, etc. (Nunan, 1989).

Factors affecting speaking performances

It is definitely sure that students are affected by factors, both subjective and objective, in the learning speaking process. The subjective factors are pronunciation, grammar, vocabulary, fluency, accuracy, confidence, anxiety, listening ability and motivation, and the objective factors include time pressure, planning, the standard of performance, feedback from teachers or peers and the amount of support (Tuan & Mai, 2015).

In this study, there are 5 factors that come from subjective ones will be mentioned to analyze.

Pronunciation:

Pronunciation is a way of speaking a word, especially a way that is accepted or generally understood. Luoma (2004) defined pronunciation as "the sound of speech that can refer to many features of the speech such as individual sounds, pitch, speed, pausing, stress, and intonation". To be like native speakers, students usually spend lots of time to imitate their pronunciation of a word or a sentence. However, the most effective way to improve or achieve good pronunciation is "repeating sounds and correcting them when produced inaccurately" (Gilakjani, 2016). Because it directly contributes to the success of the communication process and both the speakers and their listeners certainly feel horrible if a word is mispronounced.

Vocabulary:

Vocabulary is one of the linguistic factors besides pronunciation and grammar. Vocabulary is the number of words that a language learner is already known and can be used to communicate immediately or express what they want easily. In other words, "vocabulary is the words we teach in a foreign language" (Ur, 1996). *The communication process can not be started if the speakers do not have their own vocabulary. It is affirmed by Wilkins (1972) that "without grammar very little can be conveyed, without vocabulary nothing can be conveyed".*

Fluency:

Fluency is another necessary aspect of a successful speaking performance. According to Wikipedia, "fluency is the property of a person or of a system that delivers information quickly

and with expertise”. That means its role is to make the communication smoother, without having to stop or pause many times to think about something as grammar, translating from your own language to English in your mind, etc. and save the time of both communicative subjects. Fluency is “not only knowledge of the language, but also the ability to process information and language on the spot” (Harmer, 2007). Besides using correct grammar, the students need to have the ability of quick response with messages or information from materials or other speakers.

Confidence:

Confidence is a feeling that you are approximately sure about yourself and your abilities (Cambridge dictionary). Most students find it problematic to learn and improve their speaking presentation because of lacking of confidence. “Lack of confidence is the greatest problem which was influenced by the lack of vocabulary of the students. There are many students who want to be a master in speaking English but they do not know how to reach it” (Unej, 2016). Moreover, lack of confidence makes students feel scared or shy, even they know clearly the topic in the speaking periods.

Grammar:

Grammar is regarded as the language structure of sentences where each element has its own position and role. The purpose of grammar is to help the learners make a sentence that the others are able to catch their meaning completely. Students always suppose that it is so significant to learn grammar before learning to speak. It is synonymous that, when studying grammar, students frequently separate it from speaking practicing instead of applying immediately. Actually, in daily conversations, people usually speaking English by combining words altogether, not paying much attention to grammar.

Based on the analysis above, 5 hypotheses will be included in this study to figure out factors affect speaking performances of HUFU English – majored students and set out as follow:

- H1: Pronunciation affects speaking performances.
- H2: Vocabulary affects speaking performances.
- H3: Fluency affects speaking performances.
- H4: Confidence affects speaking performances.
- H5: Grammar affects speaking performances.

10. Methodology

Participants

The participants of the study include 7 teachers who have many years of experience in teaching speaking skill for both English-majored and non-English-majored students and 43 students. All of them were randomly selected from the Faculty of Foreign Languages at Ho Chi Minh City University of Food Industry (HUFU). These 7 teachers The students are selected unintentionally from the 1st to the 3rd year (of this school year) to make the data more reliable and objective.

Research Design

To analyze the collected data, the descriptive methods were used. The result was applied to test the hypotheses and rank of factors affecting the speaking performances of English-majored

students at HUPI. The data were processed by using Excel software to illustrate the answers in words into percent.

Research Instruments

The survey was created by using Google Form and separately delivered to the participants to collect data. The survey was very easy to comprehend and consisted of 5 statements in each section (for teachers and students) in which they were asked to choose the answer which is the most appropriate. Five statements with five closed choices were about the influential levels of 5 factors as Pronunciation, Vocabulary, Fluency, Confidence, and Grammar. Both sections had the same questions and answers.

11. Result and Discussion

The results of this survey are expected to be helpful for both teachers and students at the HUPI Faculty of Foreign Languages. The responses from the participants were collected by Google Spreadsheet which is linked with the survey and converted into a percentage to present on the figures below. The orders of statements in the survey are similar to the ones of the hypotheses.

Figure 1: Pronunciation

Figure 1 shows the result that 100% of teachers and most of students equivalent to 90.7% chose 'strongly agree' and 'agree' options. It could be inferred that speaking performances are mostly affected by pronunciation. At school, based on the designed curriculum, the teachers do not have enough time to help each student practice new vocabulary perfectly. However, the students are lethargic to practice and improve by themselves outside the classroom, which results in their anxiety of pronunciation. One more reason is that the students have a habit of speaking their mother tongue in English lessons with Vietnamese teachers or when they are asked to work in pairs or groups. Besides, the minority of students found that pronunciation does not strongly affect the oral performances. Thornbury (2005) said in his book that pronunciation is the last aspect of the language learning process that students concentrate on.

Figure 2: Vocabulary

Figure 2 represents the result of vocabulary affecting speaking performances. There are 85.7% of teachers and 86.1% of students agreed and strongly agreed with the statement of the survey. Lacking of vocabulary is related to pauses or stops in the students' performances and "considered as a big source of stress" to the students (Bhattacharya, 2017). Students are hardly able to present their ideas or thinking verbally if they do not know the meaning of words (León & Cely, 2010). On the contrary, a part of the participants strongly disagreed that vocabulary has quite an effect on speaking performances. This could be because it is not important to use vocabulary which belongs to higher levels or complex one as specialized vocabulary (words with a low frequency) in speaking presentations. For university students, especially English-majored students, they have enough basic vocabulary to speak. Because it has been a long time since the start of learning English.

Figure 3: Fluency

According to the result in Figure 3, the majority of the participants agreed with the third hypothesis, which corresponds with 100% of the teachers and a 76,7% are students. Most of the students are worried about making mistakes and as a consequence of this, their performances will appear many pauses or hesitancy. Therefore, they do not pay much attention to what they want to say and of course, lose the listeners' interest. When they are asked to speak English, they usually tend to think about what they want to say in their mother tongue first and translate it into English afterward. In contrast, fluency is not supposed to be the influential factor of speaking performance by other students of the survey. They argued that students can not be asserted not fluent if their words include pauses or stops because it also depends on the situation in which they are in. Additionally, the thing they most take an interest in is what they want to say and whether the listeners can catch up with it.

This figure reveals the result of the fourth statement in the survey. 14.3% of the teachers strongly disagreed and 7% of the students disagreed. They believed that the confidence factor does not impact on speaking performance. To explain this, many reasons were given. One of the reasons is that they got to know and became familiar with English at an early age; consequently, speaking English is an automatic reflex to them. While the rest of the participants viewed confidence as a big influential factor. When making a presentation in front of the class or crowded people, the students always feel so anxious that some of them need a certain time to calm down or can not even speak anything. And in English lessons with foreign teachers, they keep silent all the time. Based on the study about learners' anxiety, self-confidence and oral performances at Kunsan National University, Park and Lee (2015) affirmed that there is a correlation between lacking confidence or feeling anxious and the oral performances.

Figure 5: Grammar

Figure 5 points out that less than 80% of the teachers and 60% of the students stated grammar affects the speaking performances. They claimed that it would be prioritized to learn grammar before they learn to speak. This is the reason why most of the students spend much time on studying grammar but it is not effective at all. Meanwhile, there are 28.6% of the teachers and 41.8% of students thought that grammar does not make an influence on speaking performances. In other words, they mean grammar is an additional factor that facilitates the listener to completely understand and catch up with what the speaker is saying.

12. Conclusion and Suggestions

Based on the collected data, the order of factors is arranged from the factor that has the most percentage to the least one as follows (1) Pronunciation, (2) Fluency, (3) Vocabulary, (4) Confidence, and (5) Grammar. That additionally signifies the influential level of factors to the speaking performances of English-majored students at HUFU. The result of the study points out that the students in the sample size are coping with many problems as (1) they mostly speak Vietnamese instead of English in the English lessons, (2) they are in the habit of firstly translating what to say from Vietnamese into English in their mind, (3) they do not remember the meaning of words, (4) they are afraid of being commented by teachers and peers, (5) they pay much attention to grammar when they speaking. This study is carried out with small sample size, so it is suggested to be done other researches in the future with both the whole English-majored and non-English-majored students to have a general view of factors affecting their speaking performances or divide them into the first year, the second year, the third year or the fourth year for a specific one.

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APPENDIX

Survey questions for teachers and students about factors affecting speaking performances of HUFU English-majored students

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
<i>Pronunciation</i> affects your students'/your speaking performance(s)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
<i>Vocabulary</i> affects your students'/your speaking performance(s)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
<i>Fluency</i> affects your students'/your speaking performance(s)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
<i>Confidence</i> affects your students'/your speaking performance(s)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
<i>Grammar</i> affects your students'/your speaking performance(s)	<input type="checkbox"/>				

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